

Research

Juridical study of the role of international committee of the Red Cross on humanitarian assistance in the international humanitarian law perspective: Case study of Boko Haram in Nigeria

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Abstract: *The ICRC is one of the oldest international organizations in the world and since its establishment until now the ICRC has experienced many obstacles, but in reality the existence of the ICRC as an international organization has so far remained undeniable. The main objective of this research is to examine the role of the ICRC in dealing with internal violence in Nigeria. The protection provided by the ICRC to victims of the Boko Haram case is based on the 1949 Geneva Conventions, Additional Protocol II 1997 and customary international law. This legal research methodology draws data from books, journals, ICRC annual reports, websites on the internet, and other relevant sources. By providing protection to the victim of Boko Haram, the ICRC has provided several humanitarian and such as; donation of food and water, health care, care for displaced persons and promotion of international humanitarian law. The ICRC's role in assisting non-international armed conflict in Nigeria also needs the help of all parties and the war activist in respecting international humanitarian law other related sources. Nigeria's struggle against the jihadist group Boko Harm has not yet been settled, although the government has declared the rebels defeated. More soldiers died in seemingly endless wars, but the military kept their deaths.*

Keywords: *ICRC, Protection of the Victim of war, Non-International Armed Conflict, Boko Haram, humanitarian law.*

I. Introduction

Boko Haram is a militant organization who has purpose to declare an Islamic State in Nigeria. Boko Haram was established on 2002 in Maiduguri under a leadership of Muhammad Yusuf who has successfully collaborated with Al-Qaeda [1]. On 2009, Muhammad Yusuf died and replaced by Abu Bakar Shekau on 2010. In effort to eradicate Boko Haram, Nigerian

Government has formed JTF (Joint Task Force) to ensure the peace, order, and stability in Nigeria. Nigeria, the most populous nation in Africa, located in the west of the sub-Saharan, richly endowed with natural mineral and human resources is no doubt a nation with great economic potential for the future. The Nigerian state has been locked in a brutal hostility with Islamic insurgents over the last five years. At the heart of her challenges is the grave security threat unleashed on the entire nation by the Islamic extremists called Boko Haram. The challenges and effects of Boko Haram in Nigeria are extremely grave especially in the northern part of the country where the activities of the insurgency are preponderantly localized [2].

The hostility has resulted in the loss of thousands of lives and destruction of properties worth millions of Humanitarian Law as a branch of Public International Law is not widely known by the wider community. Not many people think that Humanitarian Law is a new name for the Law of War. Humanitarian law does not blame the reasons why a country takes up arms. The purpose of Humanitarian Law is to provide protection and assistance to those who suffer and become victims of war, both those who actively participate in hostilities, and those who do not participate in hostilities. Humanitarian law regulates international armed conflicts [3] (international armed conflicts) and non-international (non-international armed conflicts). The International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) is an International Red Cross known as an organization that provides assistance in international armed conflict and internal violence. The ICRC is not only engaged in the field of health as the Red Cross at the national level of the country in general. The ICRC has a special task especially in upholding the dissemination of International Humanitarian Law [4].

United Nations imposes sanctions on Boko haram:

- UN sanctions are at the request of the Nigerian government for assessing these militant groups increasingly disturbing and disturbing peace. Previously Nigeria had for years refused external assistance because it insisted that Boko Hara was a local problem.
- As a result of Nigeria's attitude, the UN Security Council even imposed sanctions for two years on Nigeria.
- From a number of investigations, according to the UN Sanctions Committee, Boko Haram was proven responsible for the attacks and kidnappings in Nigeria and Cameroon. They are also very active in carrying out attacks in Chad and Nigeria.

Barriers are also from Nigeria where there is a refusal from Nigeria against UN military forces stationed in Nigeria. Because this conflict is a non-international armed conflict, the Security Council must respect the jurisdiction of a country. UN security in this case is to fully support and give a mandate to African Union to fight Boko Haram through the Multinational Joint Task Forces. The special role held by the ICRC is the role assigned to it by countries through several instruments of International Humanitarian Law. The ICRC as an organization and non-state actor mandated by the international community to be the guardian and bearer of International Humanitarian Law through the Geneva Conventions of 1949.

Humanitarian Law allows the ICRC to ensure that humanitarian rules in warfare are respected. This makes the implementation of International Humanitarian Law important and relevant to the ICRC which acts as a promoter in an effort to minimize the impact of armed conflict or make war more humane. The ICRC has the nature of being a customary law which means that it can apply anywhere without the need for ratification. Humanitarian assistance is provided by humanitarian organizations in order to carry out its functions [5]. The forms of assistance that the ICRC does are such as organizing wounded on the battlefield, helping search for missing persons in armed conflict, organizing resistance, and providing care to civilians. In the ICRC's efforts to provide humanitarian assistance, the ICRC acts as a neutral mediator. The ICRC must not side with anyone and must not be involved in conflicting state affairs. In carrying out its difficult role, the ICRC often experiences obstacles to entering conflict areas and providing humanitarian assistance.

The ICRC's obstacle in carrying out its mission was also experienced in the Boko Haram case. Boko Haram is a militant organization that wants to establish a "pure" Islamic state in Nigeria. This group is known to attack the government, places of worship, and public places. Boko Haram has violated international humanitarian law. The Boko Haram movement is categorized as non-international armed conflict. In the common article 3 to Geneva Convention there is the ICRC's authority to be able to offer its humanitarian assistance in any non-international armed conflict. This is the basis of the ICRC to declare its readiness to carry out its duties under humanitarian law. Therefore, this research would like to elaborate further on the role of the ICRC in assisting the enforcement of International Humanitarian Law and also the obstacles and challenges faced by the ICRC in providing humanitarian assistance by carrying out the Boko

Haram case study approach. Writing this article with the title “**Juridical study of the role of international committee of the Red Cross on humanitarian assistance in the international humanitarian law perspective: Case of Boko Haram in Nigeria**”.

Based on the description in the background above, a problem can be formulated related to what is the role of the International Committee of the Red Cross in non-international armed conflict in Nigeria, in the Boko Haram Case and what are the obstacles faced by the International Committee of the Red Cross in providing humanitarian assistance in the Boko Haram case?

II. Materials and methods

The study case was conducted with an analytical descriptive research method that aims to explain the role of the ICRC in providing humanitarian assistance to non-international armed conflicts in the Boko Haram case in Nigeria and to identify the obstacles faced by the ICRC in carrying out activities to protect victims of internal violence in Nigeria in the Boko case Haram. Then do a careful analysis to answer the problem formulation [6].

Legal research according to Soerjono Soekanto is a scientific activity that is based on certain methods, systematics, and thinking aimed at studying one or several specific legal phenomena by analyzing them [7]. In an effort to achieve the objectives of this study, the approach used is the socio legal research method. Socio legal research method is a legal research method that functions to be able to see the law in the real sense and examine how the law works in a community environment [8]. The research specifications used in this research are analytical descriptive, that is, describing the applicable laws and regulations that are associated with legal theories and the practice of implementing positive laws concerning related issues.

The purpose of using qualitative methods is because the researcher tries to understand the symptoms in such a qualitative way and does not require quantification, because the symptoms do not allow to be measured accurately in numbers.

III. Result and analysis

On the general conditions of the Boko Haram Conflict, at the beginning, Boko Haram is an Islamic militant rebel group originating from Maiduguri, an area in northeastern Nigeria that is part of Borno State. They are based in Northeastern Nigeria, North Cameroon and Niger. This organization is based on Islamic sharia and opposes Western educational culture. Boko Haram

was founded in 2002 by Mohammed Yusuf with the aim of establishing a "pure" Islamic state based on the Shariah law and stopping what is considered westernization. Therefore in achieving their goals, Boko is haram to attack and detonate bombs in churches, mosques, police stations, schools, universities, and government buildings and also mislead innocent people by making him a suicide bomber [9].

Boko Haram has carried out armed attacks on civilians since 2011. In August 2014, Jama'atul Ahlis Sunna Lidda'awati wal-Jihad ("People Committed to the Propagation of the Prophet's Teachings and Jihad") known as Boko Haram declared itself as an Islamic state [10]. From July 2014 to March 2015, Boko Haram controlled 70 percent of the Borno region. The area that has been successfully under the authority of Boko Haram until January 2015 consists of 20,000 m², equivalent to the size of the country of Belgium.

As a result of the Boko Haram Attack, the Boko Haram attack had a serious impact on several aspects in Nigeria namely: (1) *Safety Impact* : The Boko Haram rebellion in Nigeria has posed serious security challenges to Nigeria in the sense that people have violated their rights to freedom caused by fear of being exposed to the Boko Haram attack. Especially in parts, northern Nigeria where Boko Haram has taken over the area by planting bombs and also brutal attacks on innocent souls. (2) *Economic Impact*: The economic impact of the rebellion militancy in Nigeria can be seen from two different perspectives. There is an effect that attacks the country itself, namely Nigeria, specifically citizens of Bauchi, Borno, Yobe, and neighboring countries. Citizens' anxiety causes migration from one place to another. Borno and Yobe suffered economic paralysis because thousands of people died in the bloody campaign of Boko Haram. Boko Haram not only led to the closure of businesses in conflicting areas but also to other regions in Nigeria. (3) *Social and Political Impact*: the Boko Haram uprising in Nigeria has drastically reduced the performance of governments in the affected region. Although the government likes to promise safety to citizens to get sympathy from the people, it can be seen that President Goodluck Jonathan failed to eradicate Boko Haram. The activities of Boko Haram have made the assumption that all Muslims are extremists. Nigerian people avoid traveling to northern Nigeria, the area where Boko Haram is occurring. (4) *Impact of Diplomatic Relations*: the Impact of Diplomatic Relations is the consequence of the Boko Haram rebellion on relations between Nigeria and other nations of the world. The Boko Haram rebellion has had a negative influence

on Nigeria's relations with other nations in the world [11]. Bombings, kidnappings and hostages (both ransom and without ransom request), especially to foreigners, not only disturb the citizens of the world but also include the international community. The United States warns its citizens not to go to parts of Nigeria. Nigeria has also been categorized as a country with a list of world terrorists which was later removed. (5) *Impact of the Unity of the Nigerian State*: Nigeria is a heterogeneous Nation because it has more than 300 ethnic groups living together as a unitary state. But it is unfortunate because of the Boko Haram rebellion, the unity of the Nigerian state was shaken especially the State of Northern Nigeria. Boko Haram forces in action want to build a new state, namely the Islamic State; this threatens the unity of the State of Nigeria.

III.1. Non-international Armed Conflict (NIAC)

It is crystal clear from the definition of armed conflict by the ICTY (International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia) that the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria is an Armed Conflict. The credibility of this assertion could be gathered from the fact that the Boko Haram sect is an armed group that has over a long period engaged the armed forces of Nigeria in very brutal hostilities which have left scores of people dead and properties worth millions of naira destroyed [12]. Fighting in northern Nigeria has reached the category of non-international armed conflict. First, the war took place between government armed forces and non-state armed forces in the region. Conflict occurred between the Boko Haram forces and the JTF (Joint Task Force) which is a government force formed to stop the Boko Haram rebellion movement. Second, confrontation has reached a minimum level and the parties involved show the existence of a minimum of an organization. The intensity of drinking can be seen from the long duration of the Boko Haram rebellion from 2009-2016. The weapons used are also professional warfare weapons; the number of victims to date has been more than 13,000 people. The parties involved in the Boko Haram organization also have a command force structure and can maintain military operations. In 2013 the Office of the Prosecutor in the International Criminal Court (ICC) has determined the Boko Haram conflict as a non-international armed conflict. Investigations by the ICC continue to this day.

Based on Article 3 common to the Geneva Conventions 1949, non-international armed conflicts are the declaration of a war involving one or more non-State armed groups. There are 2 requirements or conditions for these situations to be classified in non-international

armed conflicts. First, the level of intensity of hostilities resulting from armed conflict must reach a minimum level. Secondly, a group of non-governmental elements involved in the conflict must be considered "party to the conflict" or, in other words, must organize armed forces. Additional Protocol II of 1977 to the Geneva Convention of 1949 expands Article 3 common to the Geneva Convention of 1949 without modifying the existing conditions of application. He suggested that non-governmental parties be able to conduct sustained and concerted military operation and to apply this Protocol. Additional Protocol II 1977 can be applied between state armed forces and dissident armed forces or Insurgent of armed conflict. In fact, common article of Geneva Conventions of 1949 does not apply to armed conflict between non-state armed groups [13].

III.2. The War Crimes and Crimes against Humanity and Nigerian obligations under international Humanitarian Law

The War Crimes committed by Boko Haram and the Nigerian Government during the war period by attacking civilians who are protected objects in warfare [14]. War crimes if directed at the population with widespread or systematic attacks can be categorized as crimes against humanity The Nigerian government and Boko Haram have been proven to have committed war crimes and crimes against humanity in carrying out their actions. This can be seen in its action to attack and even kill civilians; the attack was carried out widely and systematically under an organized leadership. Humanitarian law refers as a standard of humanity and limits for the means and methods of military operations. The ultimate goal is to limit human suffering in times of armed conflict. Nigeria is a party to the four Geneva Conventions of 1949 and also the two additional protocols, as well as the principles of Humanitarian Law. Many specific rules contained in the agreement are also part of International Customary Law and this binds all parties to a conflict, including non-state parties [15]. Violation of Humanitarian Law in the case of Boko Haram's rebellion against these regulations can be categorized as war crime. The following are principles of International Humanitarian Law that have been violated by Boko Haram and the Government Forces [16].

Firstly, The Distinction Principle is a fundamental rule of international humanitarian law is that the parties to the conflict must at all times differentiate between civilians and

combatants. Attacks should only be made against combatants and may not be directed at civilians [17]. This principle aims to distinguish between civilian objects and military objects. The Boko Haram forces did not differentiate between the Government Armed Forces and Civilians. Boko Haram attacked both sides indiscriminately. The policy of attacking Boko Haram was that they attacked every civilian who was deemed unbelievers (disbelievers) with their teachings. Boko Haram has violated the principle of distinguishing international humanitarian law. Violation of the principle of differentiation was also carried out by the JTF from the Nigerian Government. JTF often kills civilians suspected of being part of Boko Haram without communicating first. This causes JTF to be misdirected and many sacrificed civilians in the Boko Haram rebellion.

Secondly, normality principle for every person protected must be guaranteed to be able to live a normal life as in a situation where there is no armed dispute. Its application, such as prisoners of war is not criminal, because the act of detention is temporary as a preventive and security measure must end after the armed conflict ends. Kidnapping and imprisonment of a civilian by Boko Haram was carried out continuously in a long period of time. Starting from kidnapping and continued with murder, cruel treatment, and deeds that demean the prisoners of war. Some abductees were eventually released, but many abductees were killed before being released.

Thirdly, the principle of military interest is the principle implies that each party to the dispute has the right to take every action that can result in the success of a military operation, but does not violate the laws of war. The parties are allowed to use all their military power in defeating the opposing party in the shortest possible time and with the smallest casualties. This principle includes the principle of limitation and the principle of proportionality.

Fourth, the humanity principle who ensures that any actions that cause unnecessary suffering (unnecessary suffering) must be prevented in the war itself. Based on this principle, the disputing party must ensure that war is carried out humanely. Torture that causes injury and causes death should be avoided. The method of war must be done humanely even when a party has been victimized. Boko Haram in carrying out his actions

also carried out kidnappings, arrests of civilians, cruel treatment, and actions that demeaned someone.

III.3. Implementation of the ICRC's Role in Non-International Armed Conflict between Boko Haram and the Nigerian Government

The application of the Role of the ICRC Based on Common Article 3 to Geneva Convention, in the Geneva Conventions, armed disputes that are not international in nature are regulated in Article 3 of the concomitant provisions of the 1949 Geneva Conventions. Common Article 3 to Geneva Convention offers protection to victims of non-international armed conflicts. Article 3 is implemented by setting standards in military manuals in accordance with humanitarian principles by applying national legislation. Article 3 General Geneva's fourth convention has made it possible to ensure basic protection and guarantee respect for the basic rights of civilians. The ICRC is always present in areas where civilians are in danger. The following article will be explained in the Common Article 3 to Geneva Convention and its relation to the ICRC's authority to offer humanitarian assistance.

Article 3 General Geneva Convention: In the case of non-international armed disputes taking place within the territory of one of the Supreme Participating Parties, each party to the dispute will be obliged to implement the following provisions:

1. People who did not actively participate in disputes, including members of the armed forces who had laid down their weapons as well as those who were no longer participating (hors de combat) due to illness, injuries, detention or other reasons no matter what, under no circumstances must be treated with humanity, without any detrimental differences based on race, color, religion or creed, sex, ancestry or wealth, or any other similar criteria.
2. For this purpose, the following actions are prohibited and will still be prohibited to be carried out against the above mentioned people at any time and in any place:
 - Acts of violence against body and soul, especially any kind of murder, containment, cruel treatment and ill-treatment;
 - Hostage taking;
 - Rape of personal honor, especially humiliating and degrading treatment;

- Sentence and execute the death penalty without precedence of a decision handed down by a court that is formed on a regular basis, which provides all judicial guarantees recognized as a necessity by civilized nations.
3. The injured and sick must be collected and treated, an impartial humanitarian body, such as the International Committee of the Red Cross, can offer its services to the parties to the dispute. The parties to the dispute must subsequently endeavor to carry out by way of special agreements, all or part of the other provisions of this Convention. The implementation of the provisions above will not affect the legal position of the parties to the dispute. Article 2 of Common Article 3 is the legal basis of the ICRC to offer assistance. In the Boko Haram case, Nigeria allowed the ICRC to enter and provide humanitarian assistance after several years. To be able to enter into conflict areas, actors like the ICRC must prioritize humanitarian missions; there is no change in mission missions. The ICRC may have an opinion, but that is not its concern. The ICRC is not tasked with conducting investigations or prosecutions of violations of international humanitarian law. ICRC staff are also exempt from the obligation to provide evidence if called upon in court procedures, because the ICRC's neutrality and access will be threatened by its impartial nature. The humanitarian assistance provided by the ICRC to victims of conflict has no effect on the qualifications of the conflict.

The aim of the SAF (The Safer Access Framework) is to assist all the international community in enhancing the effectiveness of their humanitarian services especially in situations where security and access might be compromised [18]. The ICRC must fulfill the eight elements contained in the SAF to be able to respond to humanity in Nigeria. These elements will be analyzed by the writer on the condition of the Nigeria Red Cross and the acceptance of the ICRC in Nigeria, in the Boko Haram case. The National Society of Nigeria Red Cross has a clear understanding of the political, social, cultural and economic and environmental aspects in Nigeria related to the Boko Haram case, so that it has an idea to handle the humanitarian assistance to be provided. Nigeria Red Cross has sound legal instruments and legislation. Movements carried out in accordance with the provisions of International Law and Domestic Law, such as:

- *Human Assistance on Food and Water*

ICRC in cooperation with NRC (Nigeria Red Cross) assists on the distribution of food assistance to the civilian population who suffered in the Boko Haram conflict. ICRC and NRC observed the situation in the conflict area before launching its emergency assistance. Around 325.000 internally displaced persons (IDPs) have received food and essential household items and more than 100.000 people have benefited from the ICRC's water, sanitation and hygiene operations in north-east Nigeria [19]. Refugees and people displaced by the Boko Haram case say that lack of food is their main concern. Some families have only a little rice every day to survive. The ICRC cooperates with Nigeria Red Cross to distribute food aid to civilians who were victims of the Boko Haram Rebellion Conflict.

- *Care and Health Assistance*

For people fleeing violence and movement, they experience various kinds of health problems. Women who are pregnant are forced to only have the opportunity to give birth in a place that is not conducive, namely the conflict area. Sometimes they even have to leave their newborn baby to save themselves. Doctors and surgeons also have to deal with unusual health problems, for example injury from a bomb explosion. In collaboration with the Ministry of Health Borno, the ICRC has upgraded the Mala Kachalla primary health care center in Maiduguri and trained the handling skills of the medical staff at the hospital.

- *Human Assistance on Conflict Area*

Armed conflict has invaded Northern Nigeria for years; the ICRC is trying to restore the situation of conflict-affected areas by providing humanitarian assistance. The ICRC built a water tower with a 4,000 liter tank and installed a solar powered water supply system. The ICRC renovates several facilities such as floors, ceilings, doors and windows. In partnership with the State Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, the ICRC said it participated in a campaign to vaccinate 150,000 head of cattle and 50,000 head of sheep and goats in the state. The ICRC also provided fertilizer and corn seeds for 2,000 families which enabled them to restart their farming activities. In addition to providing humanitarian assistance to civilians, the ICRC also visits prisoners in Nigeria to ascertain and assess the conditions in which they are held in more than 20 detention facilities. Meanwhile along with his findings with the Nigerian authorities, staff provides prisoners with blankets, mosquito nets and

cleaning tools to improve hygiene conditions and helps make drinking water safe and easily available.

Application of the Role of the ICRC Based on Additional Protocol II

Additional protocol II defines non-international armed protection conflicts in more detail. The aim is to develop and complete Article 3 of the General Geneva Conventions. The four Geneva Conventions and the two Additional Protocols attach great importance to child protection. The ICRC has played an active role in efforts to protect children as victims of conflict. The ICRC carries out a number of activities to protect and assist children victims of armed conflict and situations of violence. Article 4 paragraph 3 of Additional Protocol II discusses the protection of children in non-international conflicts. The following contents of the article:

Table 1: Children must receive the attention, care and assistance they need especially related to Supplement II Article 4 paragraph 3 letter a, Article 4 paragraph 3 Additional Protocol II:

<p>1. In the field of education, including religious education and decency, according to the wishes of their parents, or in the absence of parents, the desire of those responsible for the care of the children. Regarding child protection in the Protocols The role of the ICRC in protecting children in the education sector in the Boko Haram case is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The ICRC provides protection and medical care for girls who have escaped the abduction. - The ICRC seeks to be a mediator by negotiating with the Nigerian government and leaders Boko Haram. The ICRC is trying to free the abducted girls in exchange for the release of Boko Haram leaders who have been captured by the government. The ICRC is working so that these children can return and enjoy education. 	<p>2. Appropriate steps must be taken to facilitate the reuniting of separate families. Related to uniting separate families and the role of the ICRC, it can be seen that many children who are separated from their families at a very early age. This happened because of the massive kidnapping of children by Boko Haram and also an attempt to run away from the child to save him so as to separate them from family members. The ICRC identifies and records children who are separated from their families and disseminates the information to all regions both nationally and internationally through its stakeholders and the various media that it has in collaboration with the Nigerian Red Cross in collaboration to receive complaints about missing persons. The ICRC also disseminates photographs of missing persons and links separated families with telephone calls made by ICRC [20].</p>	<p>3. The ICRC provides data on the number of civilians who are in conflict through cooperation with other humanitarian agencies. The ICRC cooperates with other humanitarian agency organizations to record the number of civilians and the number of victims and missing persons in order to expedite their humanitarian assistance. The ICRC collaborates with the UN Office of the Coordinator for Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), the UN High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), and the World Health Organization (WHO) [21].</p>
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Obstacles faced by the ICRC

Firstly, the internal obstacles are the obstacles that exist within the ICRC itself in carrying out its duties. The following will describe the internal obstacles faced by the ICRC:

- Lack of funding for humanitarian assistance operations. The ICRC expressed matters relating to the need for funds to help even more victims in Nigeria. Aid is still not

reaching hundreds of thousands of people, however, owing to a shortfall in overall funding. Much more needs to be done to meet the dire needs of the victims of the Lake Chad crisis [22].

- Programs that are not well implemented. Access to adequate housing is the most urgent needs of the victims. With regard to the large number of victims, the ICRC has had difficulty in meeting the number of tents and temporary shelters for shelter.

Secondly, the external obstacles this is the external obstacles that arise in the ICRC mission to carry out its humanitarian mission. The following obstacles will be explained.

Difficult Access to provide assistance to humanitarian operations	Lack of confidence from the Nigerian Army towards the ICRC
<p>The ICRC found it difficult to provide humanitarian assistance in the form of food and personal needs as well as health care. This is due to the condition of the road that was destroyed by the conflict worsened by the flood disaster that occurred in Nigeria. The supply of goods that are usually imported from the capital city of Abuja has stopped and the ICRC can only rely on supplies from the local market. Communication lines are cut off and electronics are totally dead also slowing down access to work from humanitarian organizations such as the ICRC in carrying out its mission.</p>	<p>The Nigerian Army treats workers from the ICRC with suspicion and anxiety. It is not uncommon for soldiers to accuse humanitarian officials of being part of Boko Haram's sympathizers or rebellion. Hassan, one of the officers, said that sometimes confronting the army increased the workload of humanitarian workers because they behaved badly and were hostile to the workers [23].</p>

IV. Conclusion and recommendation

The implementation of the role of the ICRC in the Boko Haram Rebellion case that occurred in Nigeria is intended to provide protection for the rights of civilians and combatants injured in non-international armed conflicts. The ICRC's authority to be able to offer its humanitarian assistance is contained in the Common Article 3 to Geneva

Convention. Nigeria is a country that ratified the Geneva Convention and its two additional protocols.

Nigeria is bound by Geneva law and obliged to respect international humanitarian law. Based on this the ICRC provides humanitarian assistance in the form of food, health care, the discovery of missing persons, to civilians and injured combatants and refugees. The ICRC also plays a role in providing special protection for children contained in Additional Protocol II. The ICRC searches for missing children, and collects data with children who are separated from their families, the ICRC promotes the principle of non-recruitment of child soldiers and demands its right to liberate children individually. The ICRC's obstacle in providing security assistance in the non- international conflict of the Boko Haram rebellion is divided into internal and external obstacles. Internal obstacles include: the limited cost of the ICRC in carrying out its work, the program does not run well because it still lacks the number of camps for shelter. External obstacles in the form of: difficult access to reach conflict victims due to damaged roads and flooding along with extinguished electronics and telecommunications, and the lack of confidence of the Nigerian army towards ICRC officers.

The application of International Humanitarian Law in Nigeria was not fully implemented. Both of them have violated the Distinction Principle in the hostilities of non-international armed conflicts. Boko Haram has violated common article 3 common to Geneva Convention 1949, article 27, 30, 34, 50 of Geneva Convention 1949. Meanwhile, Nigerian Government also violated article 3 common to the Geneva Convention 1949, article 27, 31, 32, 50 of Geneva Convention 1949. Nigerian Government violates article 7 of Additional Protocol 1977.

For recommendation, State should sensitize its military forces on the rules of war so as to render protection on civilian population should they participate in peace keeping assignment in the future. Internally Displaced Persons living in camps should be returned to the main cities for the avoidance of further attacks by the belligerents through suicide bombings, this is because their continue stay in the camps contribute to further attacks on them or encourage laziness on their part.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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